

Empowering students, developing agency: A dual case study exploring Irish post-primary teachers' experiences of implementing language and learning supports for students with English as an additional (EAL)

David Larkin

david.larkin9@mail.dcu.ie

Abstract

Recent Central Statistics Office (CSO, 2021) figures have shown that Ireland's newcomer population is now over 640,000 which constitutes 12.9% of the total population, a figure that has been on an upward trajectory since 2015. This rise in newcomer families has meant that Ireland's post-primary schools have become more multicultural, multilingual and diverse educational spaces, with an estimated 12% of all post-primary students classified as newcomer students. As a result, post-primary teachers' have had to adapt their teaching pedagogies and methodologies to support, accommodate and include these learners. This paper is part of a concurrent doctoral thesis which aims to explore Irish post-primary teachers' experiences of implementing language and learning supports for students with English as an additional language (EAL) in a Delivering Equality of Education in Schools (DEIS) setting and in a non-DEIS school using a dual case study design. As data collection and analysis are ongoing, the paper has three objectives. It will (i) provide an analysis of research and policy relating to the cultural inclusion of the children of new-comer families in post-primary schools for whom English is an additional language (ii) provide a rationale and description of the methodology used in the research study and (iii) provide a rationale for and analysis of the benefits and limitations of the theoretical and conceptual frameworks that underpin the study.

Keywords: Linguistic diversity, cultural diversity, multiculturalism, support for students with English as an additional language, inclusion.

Introduction

The effect of globalisation has contributed to bilingualism (where people can socially converse in at least two languages) being the norm for seventy percent of the world's population (Skinner and O'Toole, 2018). In the US and UK, where populations are globally some of the most culturally and linguistically diverse, bilingualism is apparent across many major cities. In the US, for example, one-third of all students enrolled in elementary or secondary school are ethnic minorities (Griner and Stewart, 2012), a statistic that is on an upward trajectory. In the UK, newcomer families constitute 14% of the population with an

estimated 350 different languages spoken (National Institute Economic and Social Research [NIESR], 2019). In addition, 16.6% of students in the UK are ethnic minorities with English as an additional language (NIESR, 2019).

Ireland has also seen an increase in newcomer families in the past two decades. During the 1990's a period of war and conflict in Eastern Europe forced many ethnic groups to flee their homes and search for asylum and refuge in Western Europe. Simultaneously, Ireland was experiencing an economic boom where the possibility of paid employment, safe and affordable housing and future prosperity positioned Ireland as an attractive destination for newcomer families (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2010; Darmody *et al.*, 2016). The EU accession in 2004 saw the increase of the European Union from fifteen to twenty-five States which ensured the unrestricted and freedom of travel for many Eastern Europeans to the west, and in particular, Ireland and the UK (OECD, 2010). As a result, Ireland has also experienced a demographic change in student populations at primary and post-primary level.

While the CSO provides immigration statistics annually, very little is known in understanding teachers' experiences of implementing language and learning support for newcomer students with EAL. Thus, the author's doctoral thesis aims to explore post-primary teachers' experiences of responding to the challenge of implementing language and learning supports for newcomer learners with EAL. This thesis is theoretically underpinned by Gramsci's cultural hegemony framework. It is used to examine the effect of continued neo-liberal approaches to social and educational policy and how these position EAL learners in terms of their access to education as a social good relative to other social groups. In particular, it investigates teachers' perceptions of whether or not current educational policy and practice in post-primary schools serve to marginalise the children of newcomer families

for whom English is an additional language.

Literature review

Inclusion - but at what cost? Neoliberal approaches to inclusion and diversity.

Educational inequality continues to be a contentious issue in Ireland. A contributing factor to current educational inequality is the government's persistence to devise and implement neoliberal, market-driven policies that ensure an educated workforce for a diverse, globalised market. Continued fiscal investments in education will create a skilled workforce that in-turn, will make substantial returns socially, culturally and economically (Lynch, 2018). The objective of Ireland's neoliberal policies is twofold; firstly, to produce an educated workforce for the labour market domestically, and secondly to create a competitive economy that attracts international student talent, a multicultural workforce, privileges large corporate banks and businesses, and improves Ireland's international reputation as being a globally competitive market leader that attracts international investment through our internationalised education system (Bryan, 2010).

In the context of Irish education, one criticism that is aimed at Ireland adopting neoliberal, market driven social policy is that the wider socio-political agenda is preventing meaningful inclusion for EAL learners (Bryan, 2010). Meaningful inclusion, in neoliberal policy, is not shaped by using a social justice framework (Pinson, 2014) but is measured in what newcomer families can contribute to Ireland culturally, socially, and economically (Bryan, 2010). Faas (2015) formulates the argument of the "good" versus the "bad" migrant; the good migrant actively participating and contributing to Ireland's economy and society

whereas the “bad” migrant relies on state support in the form of accommodation, job seekers’ allowance and social benefits. Thus, “good” migrants may have the resources to compete in an economically competitive state while “bad” migrants continue to live off State-supported benefits. As a result, racialised structures have been created and developed over time where “bad” migrants continue to experience incidents of racism, stigma, discrimination and prejudice in society and schools.

In Ireland adopting such a socio-political position serves only to exacerbate a greater divide in Irish society, and marginalising already vulnerable groups many of whom have not had the opportunity to amass the cultural, social or economic capital to compete in a competitive labour market (Devine, 2009; Mac Ruairc, 2009; Lynch, 2018). It is only those with the sufficient cultural, social and economic capital that will prosper and thrive in a competitive State (Devine, 2009).

Theoretical perspectives: Applying Gramsci’s cultural hegemony to Irish education

One of the key advantages in using Gramsci’s hegemonic framework to examine Irish educational policies on post-primary EAL learners, is that it brings into stark relief how the Irish post-primary education system is designed to advantage the interests of dominant white middle-class groups over those of others (Kitching, 2010; Lyons, 2010). Gramsci’s cultural hegemony argues that the dominant ideology, beliefs and values that are reproduced in public institutions and society such as schools subsequently become the accepted cultural and social norms within that society, or as Gramsci calls it “common sense” (Gramsci, Hoare, and Smith, 1971). Thus ‘common sense’ within an Irish context is represented by Irish whiteness (Kitching, 2010).

Multilingualism and multiculturalism are relatively new phenomena in Irish society, particularly within educational institutions. In policy and circular documents, there continues to be a rhetoric of inclusivity and multiculturalism (Devine, 2009), however the continued harnessing of multiculturalism in policy (Kitching, 2010) ensures that the dominant cultural paradigm in Irish education, and at governmental level, continues to be white middle-class representation (Cahill, 2015). Schools within an Irish context are essentially middle-class institutions that represent middle-class interests (Kitching, 2010; Brown *et al.*, 2016) where non-committal policies and interventions are often token gestures to inclusion (Bryan, 2010). This results in schools adopting short term approaches to supporting students for whom English is an additional language rather than any long-term commitments to structural and cultural change (Bryan, 2010). Approaches that run counter to middle-class interests, although discussed at a micro level, are rarely allowed enter public policy discourse at a macro level and hence remain beyond the consciousness of the general population (Cahill, 2015). In this way, the cultural hegemony of middle class values is maintained within the Irish educational landscape.

As part of this doctoral study, the author sought to investigate i) teachers' views of effective language and learning provision for the inclusion of EAL learners and ii) the degree to which their difficulties were compounded by educational policy and social disadvantage? For this reason, the research focused on two cases; a DEIS and non-DEIS school to investigate whether socio-economic (dis)advantage contributes to or mitigates the creation of effective and meaningful inclusion for EAL learners?

Disadvantaged or socially economically marginalised? The DEIS programme in Ireland

In 2005 the government introduced the DEIS scheme to combat socio-economic and educational disadvantage in Ireland. DEIS schools, which are typically located in areas of social disadvantage and deprivation, account for over twenty-five percent of all post-primary schools (DES, 2017). The DEIS Plan, as stated on the Department of Education and skills (DES) website (now, Department of Education) “sets out the Department’s vision for education to more fully become a proven pathway to better opportunities for those in communities at risk of disadvantage and social exclusion” (DES, 2017). However, DEIS schools tend to have a disproportionately higher ratio of students from diverse backgrounds. As the majority of newcomer families do not have the cultural, social, political and/or economic capital of the host country, they have no alternative but to live in lower socio-economic areas (Lynch, 2018). Subsequently, many newcomer students attend the local DEIS school, where favourable enrolment policies are usually centred around creating inclusive and diverse environments rather than reproducing economic, social or cultural capital (Byrne *et al.* 2010; Kitching, 2010; Lyons, 2010; Devine, 2012, Faas, 2015). A limitation of such enrolment policies is that it has resulted in the ghettoisation of some DEIS schools to lower socio-economic urban areas (Byrne *et al.*, 2010).

EAL learners and Irish policy

Schools are important spaces for integrating EAL learners socially and academically (Faas, 2015) and educational research has shown that educational outcomes and pathways have a direct impact on students’ wellbeing, job opportunities and potential earnings (Devine, 2009, Lynch, 2018). To this end, there has been little in the way of government policy addressing

the educational needs of newcomer students culturally, socially and economically in Ireland. Ireland's social policy tends to formulate policy surrounding inclusive rhetoric such as integration and diversity, which is admirable in foci but fails to address the welter of EAL learners' needs.

The first policy that has directly addressed the educational needs of EAL learners was the "Intercultural Education Strategy, 2010-2015" (IES) which was introduced in 2010 by the Department of Education and Skills (DES). The IES had two main objectives:

1. **all students** experience an education that "respects the diversity of values, beliefs languages and traditions in Irish society and is conducted in a spirit of partnership"

Education Act, 1998

2. **all education providers** are assisted with ensuring that inclusion and integration within an intercultural learning environment become the norm.

Intercultural Education Strategy 2010-2015, p. 4

The IES draws its inclusive rhetoric from the Education Act of 1998, which was written in a context that acknowledges diversity in society but was ill-prepared for the mass immigration that Ireland was to experience over the following decade. By 2010, DES recognised in policy that Ireland's educational institutions have become more diverse, multicultural and

multilingual spaces and further support and access to resources was needed for learners with EAL.

As Ireland entered a global recession in 2008, the State was experiencing an economic downturn which made Ireland a less attractive country to migrate to (DES, 2010). The economic context in which the IES was produced is an important side note as there still continued to be a significant inward flow of newcomer families, and in particular, the increasing proportion of the 0-15 years old age category (DES, 2010). The demand placed on available resources in schools increased while available funding for such resources declined. In the IES document (p. xii) DES acknowledged their limitations as they state that resources are limited but change in Irish perceptions of EAL learners is not about radical change or resourcefulness. The document states that “The IES is about thinking, planning and doing things differently, conscious of diversity and the need to create intercultural environments. . . . It requires respect for difference, and a concerted and evolving change of attitude” (IES, p. xii).

The IES is admirable in its objectives in attempting to ensure an inclusive, diverse and multicultural society, and in also attempting to achieve a respect for difference and a concerted change of attitude towards children of newcomer families for whom English is not their first language. It’s also admirable in its assertion that a radical and transformative change is required where funding and resources are provided and are made easily accessible for educational institutions to develop inclusive and equitable practices. However, it was less ambitious in extending its view of this transformation to a truly inclusive post-primary education system that valued diversity and challenged hegemonic interests.

The Migrant Integration Strategy 2017-2020

The next government policy that this paper will address is the “*Migrant Integration Strategy: A Blueprint for the Future 2017-2020*” (MIS). The overarching theme of the MIS was social integration for newcomer families which would ensure inclusion and participation across Irish cultural, social, political and economic domains. The MIS states that integration is the “ability to participate to the extent that a person needs and wishes in all major components of society without having to relinquish his or her own cultural identity” (MIS, p. 11). In 2016, the economic context in which the MIS was written was one of continued economic and fiscal growth with further increased access to resources. As a result, Ireland was in a better position economically to commit to inclusive social policy initiatives. The then Minister for Justice and Equality Frances Fitzgerald stated that:

The Migrant Integration Strategy sets out the Government’s commitment to the promotion of migrant integration as a key part of Ireland’s renewal and as an underpinning principle of Irish society. The Strategy provides a framework for a range of actions to support migrants to participate fully in Irish life. The actions proposed are designed to support the integration process. They are also intended to identify and address any remaining barriers to integration.

(Migrant Integration Strategy 2017-2020, p. 2)

The MIS states that “Its primary objective is to ensure that barriers to full participation in Irish society by migrants or their Irish-born children are identified and addressed” (MIS, p. 8). In identifying and addressing these barriers, the MIS comprises twelve actions that aim to improve societal integration for newcomer families. These actions include:

- 1) general actions,

- 2) access to citizenship/long residency,
- 3) access to public services and social inclusion,
- 4) education,
- 5) employment and pathways to work,
- 6) health,
- 7) integration in the community,
- 8) political participation,
- 9) intercultural awareness and combating racism and xenophobia,
- 10)volunteering,
- 11) sport,
- 12) implementation and follow-up.

Research aims and questions

This paper is part of a concurrent doctoral thesis which aims to explore post-primary teachers' experiences of implementing language and learning supports for students with EAL in a DEIS and in a non-DEIS school. In doing so, it wishes to discover:

- the degree to which post-primary aged children of newcomer families for whom English is an additional language were seen as representing (valued) diversity within their schools or

as different from other learners in each setting?

- the degree to which current language and learning provision was deemed effective in facilitating the inclusion of EAL learners?
- Does socio-economic status figure in the effective and meaningful inclusion post-primary children of newcomer families for whom English is an additional language?

Methods

Two schools were chosen as part of a purposeful sampling strategy for two reasons:

- both schools have a student with EAL cohort of over ten percent;
- both schools have an explicit vision of creating inclusive learning environments for culturally and linguistically diverse students.

These criteria were checked by analysing the respective school websites and consulting with teachers who have previously worked there. A DEIS and non-DEIS school was chosen to ascertain whether socio-economic circumstance plays a role in EAL learners' access to, participating in and benefiting from EAL provision in school? The research method used to explore this phenomenon was a dual case study that gathered qualitative data from semi-structured interviews, supervisory walk-throughs and documentary analysis of school policies and school inspection reports.

Qualitative data will consist of conducting three semi-structured interviews with school practitioners (one mainstream teacher, one EAL and one SEN coordinator) in each

setting with various levels of teaching experience. Semi-structured interviews are useful when the researcher envisages that qualitative data will be the main source of their research project (Walliman, 2010), and will significantly contribute to the research's findings (Gillham, 2010). The rationale for conducting semi-structured interviews from school mainstream and SEN/EAL teachers is to gather a range of perspectives and voices who are knowledgeable about policy formulation and implementation, effective inclusive pedagogy, and implementing language and learning supports for EAL learners.

Field notes will be collected during each supervisory walk-through with a member of the leadership team. Structured observations are useful methods in the social sciences where people and their actions are being studied (Walliman, 2010), and are also useful when attempting to understand another culture or to develop a deeper understanding of the subcultures that may exist within an institution or organisation (Silverman, 2000; Miles and Huberman, 2002). One may get a better overall understanding of the phenomena under investigation by the participants' actions rather than what they have communicated to the researcher during the interview (Walliman, 2010).

A supervisory walk-through of the school will allow the principal researcher to closely analyse artefacts such as display materials, pictures, posters, notice boards and any other relevant material within the educational setting that the researcher will deem suitable for exploring the research question.

School policy documents on EAL, inclusion and diversity will be accessed through the school's website and school inspection reports are publicly available online. As it is commonplace within the Irish educational discourse to align EAL learners with SEN (Travers *et al.*, 2010), the author decided to examine both public documents from this study's chosen schools for clarity. School inspection reports are a reliable source of data for researchers as

school inspections are conducted by education professionals who are in an authoritative position to give an impartial, objective, credible and factual account of the performance of a school (Denscombe, 1998).

Conceptual Framework

Expert model of student success (EMSS)

Padilla's (2009) *Expert model of student success (EMSS)* will be adopted and modified to analyse post-primary teachers' experiences of implementing language and learning supports for EAL learners in a DEIS and in a non-DEIS school. Padilla's EMSS has been widely utilised across various levels of educational institutions in the United States, from elementary school to Higher Education. However, to date, it has not been applied to Irish educational research. Padilla's EMSS has also been employed across various demographic and socio-economic contexts (Padilla, 2009). Below, is a conceptualisation of Padilla's EMSS within a Higher Education context.

Figure 1: A black box conceptualisation of the student experience on campus (Padilla, 2009).

Based on the black box conceptualisation in figure 1, Padilla states that within any educational institution we know who is coming into the setting (inputs) and we know who is exiting the setting (outputs) but what we don't know specifically is what is happening within an institution and how this contributes to students graduating or "dropping out" of an educational setting. This is known as the "black box" or the student experiences within a given institution. Padilla states that we know what the inputs are as educators have access to student intersectional and quantifiable data such as gender, socio-economic status, race, ethnicity, assessments, levels of English proficiency and test scores etc. For Padilla, success is quantifiable as it is measured by those who have achieved (or not achieved) a qualification, such as a diploma or degree from an educational institution. Those who have achieved a qualification, are deemed to have navigated the education system "successfully" by socio-cultural expectations. Thus, an examination of the black box is required to explore and analyse the phenomena that contribute to student outcomes and why some students experience "success" while other students do not within similar or contrasting contexts.

Padilla's geography of barriers

Within the black box, Padilla argues that there is a geography of barriers in place that students must navigate in order to "graduate" and avoid "dropout". These barriers can range from context to context and do not affect each individual student proportionally. Some students may experience fewer or more barriers depending on their economic and cultural capital within a given institution (Lynch, 2018). Padilla argues that in order to navigate barriers within an education institution, students must develop their theoretical and heuristic knowledge. Padilla states (2009, p. 5) that "Theoretical knowledge is mostly book knowledge that is learned through coursework and formal study, whereas heuristic knowledge is locally

given and is acquired experientially in situ.” Prior to arriving in school, students have developed a certain amount of theoretical and heuristic knowledge from their own individual socio-cultural contexts. Below is a conceptualisation of Padilla’s geography of barriers.

Figure 2: Padilla’s (2009, p. 4) geography of barriers

For Padilla, one’s geography of barriers can be a number of phenomena for students such as distractions within an environment, lack of motivation, negative peer pressure, lack of resources and low teacher, parental and self-expectations (Padilla, 2009).

Using Gramsci’s cultural hegemony framework alongside Padilla’s EMSS allows the author to identify the geography of barriers that are in place for teachers when implementing language and learning supports for EAL learners.

Using and modifying Padilla’s EMSS framework to investigate post primary teachers’ experiences of implementing language and learning supports for learners with EAL in a DEIS and in a non-DEIS school

By using Padilla’s EMSS framework in conjunction with Gramsci’s cultural hegemony, this research study hopes to

- ascertain teachers’ experiences of implementing language and learning supports for students with EAL;
- how do teachers navigate EAL learners’ and the school’s geography of barriers to ensure meaningful and effective inclusion for learners with EAL;

Below, is a conceptual representation of Padilla’s modified EMSS for this research study.

Figure 3: A modified conceptual model of Padilla’s EMSS

At the forefront of Padilla’s EMSS framework is the importance of, and acknowledging student and institutional context in overcoming potential barriers to school success. Thus “success”, its definition, understanding and representation can look and be very different models in different educational institutions within different contexts. However, for this study,

“success” will be how effective each case school are in ensuring students have access to, participate in and benefit from language and learning provision, and secondly, how this provision creates a culturally inclusive educational environment within each setting,

In investigating post-primary teachers’ experiences of implementing language and learning supports in two culturally, socially and economically diverse schools, the author envisages to get a thorough understanding of the various phenomena occurring within each school’s respective “black box”, the geography of barriers that are in place, and how “successful” cultural inclusion manifests itself within each setting. It is envisaged that wider applicability of the research findings may be possible for schools with similar demographics with those participating in this research study (Timmons and Cairns, 2012).

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was granted from Dublin City University’s Research Ethics Committee (REC). All case study interviews and any subsequent data used will be anonymised in order to protect the identity of the participants. Pseudonyms will be assigned to the two case schools in this study. Prior to commencing the research study, all participants will be given a plain language statement outlining the rationale, process and data collection methods of the research. Once participants are in receipt of the plain language statement, there will be opportunities to ask questions and raise any concerns surrounding the purpose of research study. It will be the researcher’s imperative to develop and maintain a positive, non-judgemental and supportive relationship that will ensure a positive experience for the participants. Once the research study proceeds the participants will be issued an informed consent form. Informed consent is a crucial stage of the research design as it “respects the

right of individuals to exert control over their lives and make decisions for themselves” (Cohen *et al.*, 2011, p. 77). It also ensures that participants are treated with respect and dignity, are as informed as possible about the research study and thus have the autonomy to make objective decisions as to whether they wish to partake or withdraw from participating in the research study (Atkins, 2012). The informed consent will assure participants, to the best of the researcher’s ability, confidentiality and anonymity (Silverman, 2000). Participants in this study were reminded that they could leave the research process, without prior notice, at any time. Their participation in the research process would be discontinued and any subsequent data which they contributed would be destroyed immediately.

Limitations

The rationale of this study from its outset was to ascertain post-primary teachers’ experiences of implementing language and learning supports for EAL learners, and how this contributes to successful cultural inclusion within two contrasting school settings. This study’s objective was to avoid making facile comparisons between the two case schools. Rather, the study is an attempt to exemplify the complexities of constructing culturally inclusive practice for diverse student cohorts within educational settings.

Due to time constraints and the impact of Covid-19, both case studies will be completed in one week in each setting. More time in each setting would have enabled a more in-depth view of the degree to how inclusive practices are created, implemented and sustained in these settings. Because of this time frame, the amount of data collected and whether this is the “correct” data are limitations of this study. An ethnographic study would have been useful in monitoring different developments and emerging patterns over a longer period of time in

order to get a sense of how an inclusive culture is embodied. In addition, building relationships with participants over a longer period of time could reduce researcher effects on the participants and their behaviours which may have increased the subjectivity of data collection and analysis.

Conclusion

This paper has attempted to set out the rationale of investigating post-primary teachers' experiences of implementing language and learning supports for EAL learners in a DEIS and in a non-DEIS school, the methodology chosen and the theoretical and conceptual frameworks that underpin this study. The contextual landscape of Ireland as a diverse multicultural and multilingual country and its subsequent impact on post-primary classrooms highlights the imperative that we understand the complexity of issues pertaining to the inclusion of EAL learners and that post-primary teachers need to be adequately informed, supported and resourced to include them meaningfully in classrooms where diverse, multicultural and multilingual learners are valued, regardless of socio-economic circumstance. An egalitarian policy framework set out by governments that commits to equality, diversity and inclusion regardless of intersecting circumstances would benefit EAL learners in their right to access, participate in and benefit from post-primary education. It is also envisaged that this study will enable the case schools and teachers to reflect on their practice and ensure inclusive and supportive practices for EAL learners going forward.

References

Atkins, L. & Wallace, S. (2012) 'Research in education', *Qualitative research in education*.
London: sage publications.

Brown, M., McNamara, G., O'Hara, J. (2016) Quality and the rise of value-added in education: The case of Ireland. *Policy futures in education*, 14(6), pp. 810-829.

Bryan, A. (2010) Corporate multiculturalism, diversity management, and positive interculturalism in Irish schools and society. *Irish educational studies*, 29(3), pp. 253-269.

Byrne, D., McGinnity, F., Smyth, E. & Darmody, M (2010) Immigration and school composition in Ireland. *Irish educational studies*, 29(3), pp. 271-288.

Cahill, K. (2015) Seeing the wood from the trees: A critical policy analysis of intersections between social class inequality and education in twenty-first century Ireland. *International electronic journal of elementary education*. 8, pp. 301-316.

Central Statistics Office (2021) Population and Migration Estimates, April 2021. Available at <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-pme/>

populationandmigrationestimatesapril2021/ (Accessed 30th September 2021).

Cohen, L., Manion, L., Morrison, K. (2011) *Research methods in education* (7th edn.).

London: Routledge.

Darmody, M., Byrne, D., & McGinnity, F. (2016) Cumulative disadvantage? Educational careers of migrant students in Irish secondary schools. *Race, ethnicity and education*. 17, pp. 129-151.

Department of Education and Skills (2010) *Intercultural education strategy, 2010-2015*. Available at:

<https://www.education.ie/en/SchoolsColleges/Information/Intercultural-Education-Strategy/Intercultural-Education-Strategy.html> (Accessed: 5th June 2021).

Department of Education and Skills (2017) *DEIS: Delivering of opportunity in schools*.

Available at: <https://www.education.ie/en/schools-colleges/services/deis-delivering-equality-of-opportunity-in-schools/> (Accessed: 5th June 2021).

Department of Justice and Equality (2016) *The Migrant integration strategy: A blueprint for the future 2017 – 2020*. Available at:

http://www.justice.ie/en/JELR/Migrant_Integration_Strategy_English.pdf/Files/Migrant_Integration_Strategy_English.pdf (Accessed: 5th June 2021).

Denscombe, M. (1998) *The good research guide for small-scale research projects*.

Buckingham: Open University Press.

Devine, D. (2009) Mobilising capitals? Migrant children's negotiation of their everyday lives in school. *British journal of sociology of education*, 30(5), pp. 521-535.

Devine, D. (2012) Practising leadership in newly multi-ethnic schools: tensions in the field? *British journal of sociology*, 34(3), pp. 392-411.

- Education Act (1998). Dublin: The Stationery Office.
- Faas, D., Sokolowska, B., & Darmody, M. (2015) 'Everybody is available to them': Support measures for migrant students in Irish secondary schools. *British journal of educational studies*, 63(4), pp. 447-466.
- Gillham, B. (2000) *Case study research methods*. London: continuum.
- Gramsci, A., Hoare, Q. and Nowell Smith, G. (1971) *Selections from the prison notebooks of Antonio Gramsci*. London: Lawrence & Wishart.
- Griner, A.C., & Stewart, M.L., (2012) Addressing the achievement gap and disproportionality through the use of culturally responsive teaching practices. *Urban education*, 48(4), pp. 585-621.
- Kitching, K. (2010) An excavation of the racialised politics of viability underpinning education policy in Ireland. *Irish educational studies*, 29(3), pp. 213-229.
- Lynch, K. (2018) *Barriers to education facing vulnerable groups*. Written submission to the Joint Oireachtas Committee on Education and Skills. Dublin: School of Education, UCD.
- Lyons, Z. (2010) Articulating a deficit perspective: a survey of the attitudes of post-primary English language support teachers and coordinators. *Irish educational studies*, 29(3), pp.289-303.
- Manzoni, C. & Rolfe, H., (2019) *How schools are integrating new migrant pupils and their families*. National Institute of Economic and Social Research.
- Mac Ruairc, G. (2009) 'Dip, dip, sky blue, who's it? NOT YOU': children's experiences of standardised testing: A socio-cultural analysis. *Irish educational studies*, 28(1), pp. 47-66.

Miles, M. B. & Huberman, A. M. (eds.) (2002) *The qualitative researcher's companion*.

Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage publications.

Padilla, R. (2009) *Student success modelling*. Sterling, VA: Stylus publishing, LLC.

Silverman, D. (2000) *Doing qualitative research: A practical handbook*. London: Sage publications.

Skinner, B., & O'Toole, B. (eds.) (2017) Minority language pupils and the curriculum: closing the achievement gap. Conference presentation. *Marino Institute of Education*. 25 April 2017.

Taguma, M., Kim, M., Wurzburg, G., & Kelly, F. (2010) *OECD reviews of migrant education: Ireland 2010*. Paris, OECD Publishing.

Timmins, V., & Cairns, E. (2012) 'Case study research in education' in *Encyclopaedia of case study research in education*. Los Angeles: Sage publications.

Walliman, N. (2010) *Research methods: The basics*. London: Routledge.